

1 **A cell line model of HBV infection.**

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6 We studied and established a transcriptomic method of studying HBV infection *in vitro* in a HepG2 HBV
7 infection system. The cells were defined by expression of *Slc25a5* and *Slc25a43*. The cells produced high
8 levels of *IL13ra1* and expressed a suite of armadillo repeat containing proteins including *Armcx6*, *Armcx3*
9 and *Armcx5*.

10 Citations

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15 screening in the haploid system reveals *Slc25a43* as a target gene of oxidative toxicity. *Cell Death &*
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